
Clustering-Based Framework for Assessing Transportation Resilience to Flood Events

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Abstract

1 Flooding presents a significant threat to critical infrastructures (CIs), particularly
2 in Spain, which is frequently cited as the most flood-affected country in Europe.
3 The transportation sector, a crucial CI, is particularly susceptible to such events.
4 It is imperative to monitor the corresponding resilience to improve disaster
5 management efforts. With the advancements in data science and machine
6 learning, various approaches have been developed in this area; however,
7 researchers encounter challenges such as data inconsistency and reliability. This
8 paper presents a resilience assessment framework that utilises machine learning
9 and open data to evaluate the impact of floods on Spain's transportation network.
10 The analysis aims to facilitate well-informed decision-making by stakeholders
11 and government entities, thereby enhancing disaster preparedness and response.

12 1 Introduction

13 Flood effects are a significant global challenge, threatening critical infrastructures (CIs) [1, 2]. Due
14 to climate change, flood events are constantly growing in intensity and have consistently ranked as
15 the one that causes significant economic consequences in Spain, with CIs being particularly
16 vulnerable. This has led to Spain being reported as the most affected European country by such
17 calamities [3, 4]. CIs are essential to maintain vital societal functions therefore it is of utmost
18 importance to ensure their resilience to any extreme event. Implementing disaster management
19 actions can attenuate some of the flood effects in the transportation network [5, 6], minimising the
20 possible impact of disasters on the population and other CIs [7].

21 Accurately assessing the transportation resilience is crucial for generating effective disaster
22 management and risk planning [8]. This enables urban planners, policymakers, and emergency
23 management practitioners to gain insight into the impacts and implement mitigation strategies [9–
24 12]. CI resilience can be defined as the infrastructure's ability to swiftly return to its original form
25 and function post-disruption, achieved through proactive stress prevention, impact absorption, and
26 rapid recovery [13]. The resilience level can be assessed based on the infrastructure performance
27 and the disaster magnitude [13], considering infrastructure performance as the current operational
28 state of a system, which can fluctuate due to the magnitude of a disaster. The combination between
29 infrastructure performance and the disaster's magnitude determines the CI resilience level.

30 There is a demand for tools to assess CIs' disaster resilience, principally adopting quantitative and
31 accurate data [14–18]. Machine learning (ML) has expanded the scope of resilience assessments by
32 enabling the analysis of vast data. It aids in providing recommendations and making decisions across
33 diverse fields [19]. The advantages of ML include offering a resilience overview [20], providing
34 event impact insights [21], and assisting emergency services in identifying critical areas that may

35 have more significant impacts [22]. Nevertheless, current approaches lack a comprehensive
36 resilience definition, do not utilise accurate data, are tailored to specific regions, and do not consider
37 historical data [18].

38 This paper presents a resilience framework focused on CIs supported by ML clustering methods and
39 open data. The framework is applied to flood events faced by the transportation system in Spain at
40 a provincial level, offering a comprehensive resilience analysis of the evaluated events that caused
41 serious damage to the Spanish transportation system. This analysis aims to support Spanish
42 government bodies and stakeholders in making informed policy decisions.

43 2 Data

44 Our study adopts three kinds of data: event magnitude, economic losses, and supplementary
45 features. These data represent ten years (2013 - 2022) of flood events in the Spanish transportation
46 system. The event magnitude is represented by meteorological data from the Spanish State
47 Meteorological Agency (AEMET) and the associated economic losses by the Spanish Insurance
48 Compensation Consortium (CSS) [23, 24]. Regarding the event magnitude, we collected data related
49 to maximum, minimum and average temperature (in °C), average and maximum wind speed (in
50 Km/h), precipitation (in mm) and event duration (in days). For the economic losses, data related to
51 the total losses (in Euros), the number of insurance claims and the losses per day (in Euros) were
52 gathered. Lastly, the supplementary features were the event start date, the Spanish province name
53 where the event occurred, and the season. As a result, the merged dataset was generated with 2,665
54 events.

55 3 Methods

56 A three-step process to gather the data, cluster the events and analyse the results was developed.
57 Figure 1 depicts the steps, where the first step gathers data from databases and performs the data
58 cleaning. The second step develops the clustering ML methods and selects the best model. Finally,
59 the third step calculates the transportation resilience score and analyses the scores. Subsequent
60 sections provide explanations of the framework tasks that were performed.

61
62 Figure 1: The developed ML clustering framework to generate transportation resilience score.

63 3.1 Data Gathering

64 Resilience can be assessed by considering the disasters faced over a period and how they were able
65 to withstand them, reducing the resulting economic impact. Based on that, the data regarding the
66 economic losses from the CCS, the event magnitude from the AEMET and supplementary data from
67 both portals were collected. As presented in Section 2, the data related to events that occurred over
68 ten years in Spain were extracted. A cleaning step was conducted to remove inconsistencies.
69 Afterwards, a correlation analysis was used to remove related variables. The results indicated a
70 connection between the temperature and wind variables. Therefore, we adopted the average
71 temperature and wind speed. Regarding economic losses, daily losses were not used to encompass

72 both total losses and insurance claims. The correlation analysis can be found in Appendix A. Finally,
73 two sets (S1 and S2) were created to test different analyses. Set S1 includes features, while S2
74 comprises the main features related to the event magnitude (i.e. precipitation and duration) and
75 economic losses (i.e. claims and total losses).

76 **3.2 Clustering Creation**

77 After collecting the data, we utilised ML clustering techniques to uncover potential patterns between
78 event magnitude and losses. Clustering, an unsupervised learning method, employs partitioning
79 algorithms to identify patterns within unlabeled data [25]. By analysing the attributes of the clusters,
80 we can establish resilience categories based on these clusters, ranging from high resilience to low
81 resilience. We used highly adopted clustering techniques based on the selected features, including
82 K-Means, DBSCAN, OPTICS, and Gaussian Mixture (GMM) algorithms [25–29].

83 After establishing the clustering methods, we thoroughly analysed the models in task 4. We
84 evaluated the methods using the Silhouette, Davis-Bouldin, and Calinski-Harabasz indexes to
85 determine the optimal number of clusters. These indexes have shown promising results in
86 comparative studies and offer comprehensive information for selecting the optimal configuration
87 [30]. A script was created to find the best number of clusters based on these indexes and a smaller
88 number of clusters.

89

90 **3.3 Analyzing the Resilience Score**

91 The final tasks were to combine the outcomes and categorise the resilience level based on the
92 disaster level. Step 5 converted the clusters into low to high resilience categories. The score ranges
93 from 1 (high resilient) to the total number of clusters (less resilient). Therefore, low resilient events
94 can more accurately depict the resilience scenario of the transportation system in that province. After
95 that, the scores were compiled using a weighted average based on province and year, with weights
96 ranging from 1 to the maximum of categories, prioritising harmful events. Lastly, the results were
97 normalised, and a 3-year moving average (MA) was performed. The MA allows for comparisons
98 over the years and identifies correlations between provinces with similar scores in the temporal
99 analysis.

100 **4 Experiment Results**

101 As a result, the GMM with Set 2 with four clusters was the best one by analysing the generated
102 clustering performance score. With that, the GMM cluster model was adopted for the resilience
103 assessment of the transportation system. The full description of the clustering performance score of
104 all methods can be seen in Table 2. Based on the best ML model, four clusters were generated
105 (named CL-A, CL-B, CL-C, CL-D) and associated with four transportation resilience categories:
106 high, medium-high, medium-low, and low. We analysed the distribution for each feature and cluster
107 to perform the association. According to the relation between the event magnitude and economic
108 losses, the events in CL-C and CL-A were considered highly and medium-high resilient,
109 respectively. On the other hand, the CL-B and CL-D were medium-low and low resilient.

110 After associating the clusters to the categories, we attributed scores from 1 (high resilience) to 4
111 (low resilience). With this new association, the characteristics of each category are in Figure 3-A,
112 based on the features' means. This representation shows that the categories with the higher resilient
113 events (in blue and green in Fig. 3-A) have a greater value in the event magnitude and a lower value
114 in economic losses in the transportation system. Conversely, the categories with low resilient events
115 (in yellow and red in Fig. 3-A) show the opposite, with higher losses and lower event magnitude.

116 Figure 3-B shows that most events fall under category 2, characterised by low event magnitude and

117 minimal losses, which could be classified as typical floods. These typical floods can be, for example,
 118 a flash flood that only affected one road and damaged a truck or bus. This trend persists when
 119 dividing the data into high resilient (scores 1 and 2) and low resilient (scores 3 and 4) events,
 120 showing that the Spanish transportation system largely handles events with considerable resilience.

121 With the resilience categories, we calculated the score based on the province and year. Figure 4
 122 presents the evolution of the resilience of the top five most and least resilient provinces for 2022. In
 123 some cases, like in 2015 and 2021 in Zamora, no data is shown due to the absence of floods reported
 124 by CCS. Based on this analysis, Madrid achieves the highest score, being the least resilient
 125 compared with the other provinces during all the years. The opposite scenario is perceived with
 126 Pontevedra, obtaining the lowest scores compared with the top most resilient provinces in 2022.

127 Regarding the scores of these provinces, Madrid's score increased from 2013 to 2017, remained
 128 stable from 2017 to 2021, and then decreased in 2021 and 2022. This stability and decline can be
 129 attributed to governmental actions. Distinct regulations have been enacted focusing on flood
 130 preparedness and mitigation actions [31, 32]. It is important to emphasise that these initiatives do
 131 not lead to an immediate transformation. However, their impact becomes discernible in the last years
 132 of analysis. Pontevedra had a general stability, with an increase in the last three years. This increase,
 133 which led to a modest resilience decrease, was highlighted by news agencies [33, 34]. Moreover,
 134 the province has initiated projects on resilience assessments and flood strategies [35–37]. Notably,
 135 these efforts by Pontevedra are still in their early stages and may increase the resilience.

136

137 Figure 4. Top 5 most and least transportation resilient provinces in 2022. The results range from 0
 138 (green) to 1 (red), where the closer to 1, the less resilient the region.
 139

140 5 Conclusion

141 This study demonstrates a resilience assessment framework based on clustering ML models and
 142 openly available data. The generated approach can assess the resilience level of flood events that
 143 provoke economic losses to the transportation system based on the event magnitude level. We
 144 obtained the best outputs by adopting accurate data and analysing distinct clustering techniques. Ten
 145 years of flood events were classified and analysed based on the resilience level of the transportation
 146 system. With this analysis, stakeholders can understand the disaster impact and glean insights about
 147 potential CI vulnerabilities and strengths. Furthermore, stakeholders can prioritise their efforts and
 148 strategically allocate resources by examining the losses incurred by a disaster within different
 149 clusters. In conclusion, our work demonstrates that ML can be a valuable tool for decision-makers
 150 in performing resilience assessments and addressing the bottleneck in the resilience field. In future
 151 work, we plan to enhance the model and create visualisations based on the results to provide
 152 information in a straightforward way to decision-makers.

153

154

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275 **A Correlation analysis**

	Max Temp	Min Temp	Avg Temp	Wind Speed	Max Wind	Precipitation	Duration	Season	Claims	Losses per Day	Total Losses
Max Temp	1	0.88	0.98	-0.22	-0.21	-0.38	-0.094	-0.45	0.0023	0.0007	0.0056
Min Temp	0.88	1	0.96	-0.17	-0.15	-0.23	-0.025	-0.37	0.028	0.022	0.015
Avg Temp	0.98	0.96	1	-0.21	-0.19	-0.33	-0.068	-0.43	0.013	0.009	0.0031
Wind Speed	-0.22	-0.17	-0.21	1	0.96	0.31	-0.014	-0.0088	-0.0014	0.0091	0.0017
Max Wind	-0.21	-0.15	-0.19	0.96	1	0.27	-0.016	-0.0069	0.0034	0.0075	0.0027
Precipitation	-0.38	-0.23	-0.33	0.31	0.27	1	0.64	0.17	0.29	0.29	0.3
Duration	-0.094	-0.025	-0.068	-0.014	-0.016	0.64	1	0.063	0.36	0.31	0.37
Season	-0.45	-0.37	-0.43	-0.0088	-0.0069	0.17	0.063	1	7E-05	-0.0064	-0.0017
Claims	0.0023	0.028	0.013	-0.0014	0.0034	0.29	0.36	7E-05	1	0.88	0.93
Losses per Day	0.0007	0.022	0.009	0.0091	0.0075	0.29	0.31	-0.0064	0.88	1	0.93
Total Losses	0.0056	0.015	0.0031	0.0017	0.0027	0.3	0.37	-0.0017	0.93	0.93	1

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277 Figure 2. The correlation matrix between the event magnitude and event losses features

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279 **B Clustering performance score**

280 Table 2. Clustering performance score

Cluster Method	Nº of Clusters	Silhouette	Davis-Bouldin	Calinski-Harabasz
K-Means (S1)	2	0.396	1.122	1682.241
K-Means (S2)	2	0.629	0.698	3211.166
DBSCAN (S1)	3	-0.822	1.705	0.060
DBSCAN (S2)	2	0.713	0.921	619.76
OPTICS (S1)	2	-0.646	2.396	2.103
OPTICS (S2)	7	-0.581	15.064	2.930
GMM (S1)	2	0.469	0.882	2648.115
GMM (S2)	4	0.712	0.943	4887.789

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C Clustering classification

Figure 3. (A) Mean of the features by the transportation resilience categories. (B) Table with the number of events divided by each resilience category